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Leibniz on Modality and Counterparts

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, I present a novel problem for the interpretation of Leibniz's discourse about possible individuals (e.g. possible 'Adams'). Possibilia play an important role in Leibniz's philosophy: they allow him to account for freedom and contingency present in the world. I attempt to square Leibniz's discourse about possibilia with his theory of truth and the infinite analysis conception of modal notions. It turns out that this is not a straightforward matter: I argue that identity statements such as 'Caesar is Caesar' present a key challenge for this task. I consider a few options with regards to the interpretation of Leibnizian discourse about possibilia and I argue that the most charitable interpretation (also supported by textual evidence) makes use of a counterpart relation based on similarity (akin to Lewis 1968).

Keywords: *Leibniz Modality, Identity, Infinite Analysis, Counterparts*

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1 Introduction

Leibniz is often hailed as the father of possible worlds. The framework of possible worlds constitutes an invaluable theoretical resource from the point of view of modern analytic philosophy, especially modal metaphysics. How much of the current success of possible worlds should be credited to Leibniz? It is definitely the case that Leibniz made use of the notion of a possible world. But there is strong evidence that Leibniz's account of modal notions such as *necessity* or *possibility* was quite different from the modern one. On the modern interpretation of modal notions, a proposition is necessary if it is true in all possible worlds and possible if true in some possible world. In contrast, Leibniz endorsed the infinite analysis conception of modal notions. How to account for Leibniz's discourse about possible worlds and possible individuals on the infinite analysis conception?

My aim in this paper is to show that the analysis of such discourse is not straightforward given Leibniz's theoretical commitments regarding the notion of truth and his modal metaphysics. I present a novel problem (the Identity Problem) for the interpretation of the relation between *possibilia* that makes use of the Leibnizian infinite analysis conception. I also show that the problem is not trivial, given that possible worlds and possible individuals played an important role in Leibniz's attempts to solve the Problem of Contingency. Moreover, it turns out that accounts of Leibniz's discourse about possible worlds and *possibilia* presented in the literature either go against textual evidence from Leibniz's writings or suffer from the Identity Problem. I conclude that the best interpretation of Leibniz's discourse about *possibilia* makes use of a version of Lewisian (1968) counterpart relation based on similarity.

2 Leibniz's Conception of Infinite Analysis

Leibniz endorsed the thesis that every individual substance has a complete individual concept (CIC) (P, p. 95). All predicates that the individual satisfies are either contained in its complete individual concepts or are deducible from it (P, p. 95). Leibniz writes that “every individual substance involves in its perfect notion the whole universe, and everything existing in it, past, present, and future” (P, p. 90). This means that not only is all the information about the individual contained in or deducible from its complete individual concept, but also that all the information about the world of the individual are contained in or deducible from her complete individual concept. The theory of complete individual concepts is needed for Leibniz's concept containment theory of truth. Leibniz claimed that a sentence such as ‘Aristotle is a philosopher’ is true if and only if the concept of *being a philosopher* is contained² in the concept of Aristotle. Thus, proper names of individual substances such as ‘Aristotle’ pick out the complete individual concepts of individuals. This theory holds for necessary truths as well as contingent truths. A predicate that an individual satisfies only contingently is still included in his individual concept. This account can explain the truth of singular propositions about individual substances.³

The claim that the individual concept contains all predicates that an individual satisfies naturally raises the question of what the distinction between contingent and necessary truths is for Leibniz. Earlier interpretations of Leibniz employed the standard apparatus of possible worlds (e.g. Mondadori 1973): a truth is necessary if true at all possible worlds and possible if true at some

² It is not clear whether the containment of one concept in another is to be interpreted as a syntactic relation or perhaps a semantic one. See Adams (1994) for a defence of the syntactic interpretation.

³ We should note that a theory of truth for other kinds of propositions that do not make use of complete individual concepts will not be as straightforward. However, in the paper I will focus only on singular propositions about individual substances. See Adams (1994, Section 2.2) for an analysis of different kinds of propositions in Leibniz.

possible world. However, mostly due to the work of Robert Adams (1994), the currently received interpretation is that Leibniz endorsed what is referred to as the infinite analysis conception of modal notions. Under the infinite analysis conception endorsed by Leibniz, a truth is necessary if it is *demonstrable* in a finite process of analysis. A necessary proposition can be analysed in a finite number of steps (by appropriate substitutions) into *primary truths* (P, p. 87), i.e. identity statements of the form ‘A is A’ or ‘AB is A’ (P, p. 96). Furthermore, a truth is demonstrable if we can demonstrate that its negation leads to a contradiction. Contingently true propositions are the ones for which the process of analysis is infinite, i.e. we cannot demonstrate that the predicate (or its negation) is contained in the subject. A contingently true sentence such as ‘Aristotle is a philosopher’ is not demonstrably true. The concept of *being philosopher* is contained in the complete concept of Aristotle, which means that the sentence is true, but the process of analysis which would reduce ‘Aristotle is a philosopher’ into an identity statement such as ‘A = A’ is infinite (P, p. 98). Importantly, the distinction between necessary and contingent truths is not an epistemic one (but rather a logical one).⁴

On the infinite analysis conception of modal notions, possible worlds and possibilities don’t play their usual theoretical role.⁵ The modern analysis of modal discourse says that a sentence such as ‘it is contingent that Aristotle is a philosopher’ just means that there are possible worlds where Aristotle is a philosopher and worlds where he is not. However, on the Leibnizian infinite analysis conception this sentence is just analysed in terms of the containment of the concept *philosopher* in the complete individual concept of Aristotle: it is true

⁴ For instance, it is not clear that for Leibniz God could complete the infinite process of analysis. The point is that the fact that the process of analysis cannot be completed by us in case of contingently true statements is not because of our epistemic limitations, but about the way in which the predicate is contained in the complete individual concept.

⁵ I am not assuming with David Lewis (1986) that possible worlds and possible individuals are concrete.

if it is not demonstrable that the concept of philosopher or its negation is contained in the complete individual concept of Aristotle.

It seems that we would be able to easily give an account of the relation between individuals and their other-worldly counterparts under the received interpretation of Leibniz as employing the infinite analysis conception for modal notions. For instance, we would expect that all counterparts of a will satisfy all predicates that a demonstrably satisfies. However, as I will show in the next section, this is not the case. This will raise a puzzle: how to interpret the counterpart relation between possibilia?

3 The Identity Problem

In this section I will present the Identity Problem for the account of the counterpart relation based on Leibniz's infinite analysis conception. The problem shows that we cannot base our account of the counterpart relation on the infinite analysis conception. In general there are two ways to provide an account of the counterpart relation using Leibniz's infinite analysis conception. The infinite analysis conception says that if ' b is F ' is demonstrable then it is necessary. On the assumption that there are predicates which are demonstrably contained in the complete individual concepts of individual substances⁶, it seems that all counterparts of b , i.e. all possible b 's, also satisfy the predicates that are demonstrably contained in the concept of b . Firstly, one might construe the relation between counterparts as based solely on the demonstrable predicates. On such a view, b is a counterpart of a if and only if b satisfies all predicates that a demonstrably satisfies. Secondly, one might take b 's

⁶ It is not entirely clear that Leibniz took any sentences of the form ' x is F ', where x denotes a complete individual concept and F is a predicate, to be demonstrable. I follow here standard presupposition made in the literature that there are such demonstrable truths. For an interesting argument that all such truths are indemonstrable, and hence contingent, see Lodge & Rodriguez-Pereyra (2011).

satisfaction of all the predicates that a demonstrably satisfies only as a necessary (but not a sufficient) condition for being a counterpart of a .

On the first option, the counterpart relation is reflexive and transitive. That is because if a truth is demonstrable, then it is demonstrably demonstrable (Adams 1994, p. 47). Thus, if demonstrability is equated with necessity, then for all predicates F such that ' b is F ' is necessary, ' b is F ' is necessarily necessary. Therefore, if ' b is F ' is necessary then any counterpart of b is F and any counterpart of a counterpart of b also is F ; so the counterpart relation is transitive. However, such an account is unlikely to get off the ground. There is a limited number of predicates that any individual substance demonstrably satisfies. For instance, even if truths related to being a member of a natural kind, such as 'Caesar is a rational animal', are demonstrable there may not be enough such truths too distinguish between Caesar and other members of his kind. Thus, the second option is preferable: it is only a necessary condition on being a counterpart of a that one satisfies all the predicates that are demonstrably contained in a 's CIC.

Unfortunately, the view on which any b that is a counterpart of a must satisfy all the predicates that a demonstrably satisfies also faces a serious problem. The biggest problem to the account that tries to base the counterpart relation on the infinite analysis account is the problem presented by cases of identity statements such as 'Caesar is Caesar'. Let us call it the Identity Problem. There is evidence to suggest that Leibniz took identity statements to be necessary. For example, in letter to Hermann Conring (March 19th, 1678) Leibniz writes:

But we know that identical propositions are necessary propositions without any understanding or analysis of their terms, for I know that A is A, whatever may be understood by A (L, p. 187).

The above remark made by Leibniz does not seem to be merely a casual one. For in the passage which the quote comes from Leibniz explains his conception of

necessity. He states that every necessary truth can be demonstrated to be true by a 'chain of definitions' (L, p. 187). Thus, the process of demonstration starts with an identity statement and by making proper substitutions we reach the statement which we set out to demonstrate. Therefore, it seems that each step of the demonstration is an identity statement, which is derived from the previous step by a substitution. Leibniz's point in the quote above is that in order for his method of demonstration to work, the identity statements which one starts the demonstration from and which one derives in the process of demonstration have to be necessary.

However, if 'Caesar is Caesar' is demonstrable and we require that every counterpart of Caesar satisfies the predicates that Caesar demonstrably satisfies, then for any counterpart *c* of Caesar '*c* is Caesar' would have to be demonstrable. But 'Caesar' in Leibniz's semantics denotes the complete individual concept of the actual Caesar. However, it seems that in order to satisfy the complete individual concept of Caesar, one must satisfy all the predicates that are contained in the complete individual concept of Caesar, even the ones that are contingently contained by Caesar's complete individual concept. This means that any counterpart of Caesar would have to satisfy all the predicates that the actual Caesar satisfies; however, we know that Leibniz wants there to be qualitative differences between counterparts in different worlds (H, §414).

Therefore, we cannot base the analysis of the relation between Adam and possible Adams on Leibniz's infinite analysis conception of modal notions. The sentence 'Adam is Adam' is demonstrable and hence necessary. However, no non-actual individual satisfies the predicate 'is Adam', because 'Adam' denotes Adam's CIC, which contains every truth about the actual world. So even if Adam demonstrably satisfies the predicate 'is Adam', no counterpart of Adam in a non-actual possible world can satisfy that predicate. Consequently, we cannot base

the interpretation of the relation between a and its counterparts on the predicates that a demonstrably satisfies.

3.1 Potential objections to the Identity Problem

One potential worry about the Identity Problem is that it seems to entail that Leibniz was a superessentialist. Superessentialism is the thesis that if an individual satisfies a predicate F then the individual essentially satisfies F .⁷ Complete individual concepts may be interpreted as being akin to infinite conjunctions of predicates. It seems that if it is necessary for something to satisfy a conjunction than it is necessary for it to satisfy each of the conjuncts. So if we hold that it is necessary for Caesar to satisfy the predicate ‘is identical to Caesar’ and ‘is identical to Caesar’ is a conjunction of all predicates satisfied by Caesar, then it is necessary for Caesar to satisfy all the predicates that are contained in his complete individual concepts. But this is just superessentialism. The interpretation of Leibniz as a superessentialist used to be very popular, but the view has been famously criticised by Robert Sleigh (1990). If the Identity Problem leads to superessentialism, then (by *modus tollens*) we can reject the Identity Problem by rejecting superessentialism.

However, the move from the Identity Problem to superessentialism is not sound. The reason is that on Leibniz’s account of modal notions, the inference from a conjunction being necessary to a conjunct being necessary is in general invalid. It may be finitely demonstrable that some conjunction is true without it being finitely demonstrable that some conjunct is true (as long as the conjunction is infinite). A good analogy may be the case of universal quantification over an infinite domain. If we interpret a statement that involves

⁷ The superessentialist thesis is sometimes stated by using the term ‘property’ instead of ‘predicate’ (e.g. see Mates 1986, p. 92). One should be careful in using the term ‘property’ when discussing Leibniz’s philosophy, because Leibniz was a nominalist (see Rodriguez-Pereyra 2014, Chapter 2).

universal quantification over an infinite domain as an infinite conjunction, it is easy to see that the demonstration of the truth of that universally quantified statement will be shorter if we just prove the universal statement than if we were to demonstrate the truth of each instance. So the reasoning behind the Identity Problem does not entail superessentialism.

Another worry about the Identity Problem is that it seems to assume that Leibniz took identity statements to be demonstrable. However, the thought goes, identity statements should be treated like axioms that are not themselves demonstrable. This line of argumentation does not block the Identity Problem in any way, because the process of analysis that Leibniz writes about crucially relies on identity statements: the process of analysis consists of substitutions of predicates into identity statements. Identity statements of the form 'Caesar = Caesar' are simply one-line demonstrations (proofs).

The Identity Problem shows that we cannot base our account of the counterpart relation on predicates that are necessarily satisfied by an individual substance. There is an obvious worry: perhaps the problem is not very important. If Leibniz's analysis of modal notions does not make use of possible worlds or possibilia, then why would Leibniz need to talk about possible worlds and possibilia at all? Perhaps, once we have the infinite analysis conception Leibniz can dispense with possible worlds and refer to them only as heuristic devices that are useful for explanations of some phenomena, but not as something that is of independent philosophical interest. However, in the next section, I will argue that possible worlds and individuals are not mere heuristic devices for Leibniz: they play an important role in his attempt to solve the Problem of Contingency. Thus we will not be able to simply dispense with the notion of possible worlds and individuals, which means that the questions about the construction of the counterpart relation remain worthwhile.

4 Why talk about possibilia and possible worlds?

If Leibniz endorsed the infinite analysis conception, then it seems that the framework of possible worlds is superfluous. Can possible worlds and possibilia still do some useful work in Leibniz's philosophy?

There is textual evidence that Leibniz often made use of discourse about possibilia and possible worlds. For instance, in the exchange with Arnauld, Leibniz writes:

There is a possible Adam with a certain posterity, and an infinity of others whose posterity would be different. Isn't it true that these possible Adams (if one may so call them) are different from each other, and that God chose from them just one, which is precisely ours? (WF, p. 100)

Furthermore, there is textual evidence that indicates that Leibniz did not abandon his talk about possibilia and possible worlds after he stated his theory of infinite analysis. Still in 'Theodicy', which was written ca 1709 and published in 1710, Leibniz makes use of the notion of possible worlds and possible individuals:

I will show you some [worlds], not absolutely the same Sextus as you have seen (that is not possible, he carries with him always that which he shall be) but several Sextuses resembling him [...] You will find in one world a very happy and noble Sextus, in another a Sextus content with a mediocre state, a Sextus, indeed, of very kind and endless diversity of forms (H, §414).

Thus, there is evidence that possible worlds still played some role in Leibniz's philosophy after he formulated his infinite analysis conception of modal notions.

A key reason why Leibniz engaged in the talk about possible worlds and individuals was that he was trying to solve the Problem of Contingency, as

demonstrated by the quotation from the letter to Arnauld above. The challenge is to show how it is possible for God to have the freedom in creating the world. For Leibniz, God necessarily exists (S, §45, p. 22-23). Furthermore, it is in God's nature to be perfect (L, p. 146). Thus, it seems that God necessarily does what is best (H, §237).⁸ But if God necessarily does what is best, then necessarily God creates the best possible world. However, if it is necessary for God to create the best possible world, then God has no choice in creating the world: it is necessary for God to create the best possible world, so he couldn't create the world in any other way. The actual world is the best possible world. If the world had been created only slightly differently it would not be the best world. Thus, God had no choice but to create the world He actually created. The conclusion of the argument entails *necessitarianism*, i.e. the thesis that every truth is a necessary truth. Leibniz seems to have endorsed or at least to have been close to endorsing necessitarianism in his youth.⁹ However, he quickly became a fierce critic of the doctrine.

With regards to the Problem of Contingency, there exists a controversy with regards to the best solution to the problem within Leibniz's philosophy. The strategy in the literature is to argue for one of the following claims:

- (1) It is not necessary for God to choose the best possible world.¹⁰
- (2) It is not necessary for the actual world to be the best.¹¹

However, whichever strategy turns out to be the best one for Leibniz, what is required for any of them to work is that God has something to choose from. If Leibniz is to solve the Problem of Contingency, he needs possible worlds and possibilities to show that either God could have actualised different worlds and

⁸ In the passage referenced here Leibniz talks about moral necessity rather than metaphysical necessity, which opens the door for a solution along the lines of (1) below.

⁹ See Adams (1994, p. 10-11) and Newlands (2013, p. 156).

¹⁰ See Rescher (1981) for a defence of this view.

¹¹ For a recent novel argument in support of this strategy see Pickup (2014).

individuals (or that different worlds could have been best). Since possible individuals and possibilities play this important theoretical role for Leibniz it is a worthwhile task to provide our best interpretation of such talk.

It may seem like the discourse about possibilities is superfluous since Leibniz already has a conception of modal notions such as *possibility* or *necessity*. However, Leibniz's infinite analysis conception does not seem to be sufficient to fully answer the Problem of Contingency. The infinite analysis conception is sometimes criticised as not giving us *real* contingency (Pickup 2014). If '*a* is *F*' is contingently true, then still the concept *F* is contained in the individual concept of *a*; thus, the difference between necessity and contingency seems to be logical, but not metaphysical. Going back to the Problem of Contingency, would it be possible for God to create *a* such that *a* were not *F*? On the infinite analysis conception, it is possible for *a* to be not *F* if the process of analysis which shows that *a* is not *F* is infinite. This conception may show us that it is logically possible for *a* to satisfy a predicate it does not actually satisfy. However, this seems insufficient to show that God could create the world differently; it only seems to show that logical relations between concepts don't forbid it. If there is only one possible world then it is trivially best and only one that God could have created, because then there are no other worlds and consequently no worlds better than it.

In *On Freedom*, Leibniz explicitly writes that possibilities are required to reject necessitarianism:

But the consideration of possibles, which are not, were not, and will not be, brought me back from this precipice. For if there are certain possibles that never exist, then the things that exist, at any rate, are not always necessary, for otherwise it would be impossible for others to exist in their place, and thus, everything that never exists would be impossible (AG, p. 94).

The topic under discussion by Leibniz is freedom and contingency. Leibniz suggests that possibilia are what allows for freedom to exist: since there are possible worlds where I make a different choice, it means that I did not have to make the choice that I made. This suggests a further reason why possibilia are useful to Leibniz: to account for the freedom of choice.¹²

Therefore, given Leibniz's theoretical commitments, it is worthwhile to ask about the relation between actual and possible individuals. Let us call the relation that holds between Adam and possible Adams the 'counterpart relation'. There are multiple ways in which we can interpret this relation: as identity (Cover & O'Leary Hawthorne 1999), as an equivalence relation on essential properties (Mondadori 1973), as a Lewisian counterpart relation etc. My hypothesis is that the counterpart relation between possibilia in Leibniz's philosophy should be interpreted as a Lewisian (1968) counterpart relation based on similarity. In the next section, I will outline this hypothesis and show that there is some textual evidence to suggest that this is what Leibniz had in mind when he talked about possible Adams and Sextuses. I will also show that alternatives to a counterpart relation based on identity should be rejected.

5 Interpretations of the counterpart relation

5.1 Counterpart relation as Identity

After the work of Saul Kripke, the standard way to interpret the counterpart relation in modern modal metaphysics is to take the counterpart relation to be identity. However, there is good evidence that Leibniz did not allow for trans-world identity.

¹² The connection between contingency and freedom is explicated by Leibniz as follows: 'A free act is a contingent or non-necessary act of a rational creature.' (DL, p. 3)

One way in which Leibniz's philosophy has been interpreted as rejecting trans-world identity is by ascribing superessentialism to Leibniz.¹³ It seems that such an interpretation forces the denial of trans-world identity.¹⁴ If all predicates that x satisfies are such that x satisfies them essentially, then under the assumption that if a property is essential to x then x has it necessarily, it means that x could not satisfy different predicates than it actually satisfies. However, it is clear that Leibniz thinks that Sextus in a different world would satisfy different predicates than he actually satisfies, so the relation between Sextus and possible Sextuses is not identity.

However, we don't have to accept the superessentialist interpretation of Leibniz to claim that Leibniz did not allow for trans-world identity. The interpretation of Leibniz as a superessentialist has recently come under attack by Robert Sleigh (1990). On Sleigh's view Leibniz was a superintrinsicist rather than a superessentialist. Superintrinsicism is the doctrine that every predicate that an individual satisfies is intrinsic to him. Superintrinsicism is the result of adopting the following two principles (Sleigh 1990, p. 56-57):

- (1) If x is an individual substance, then C is the individual concept of x if and only if C contains all the predicates that x satisfies.
- (2) If x is an individual substance, then C is the individual concept of x if and only if for any y , if y does not satisfy some of the predicates contained in C , then y is distinct from x .

Leibniz accepted superintrinsicism. However, to make the step to superessentialism, Leibniz would have to accept the following:

- (3) For any F , if F is intrinsic to an individual x , then F is essential to x .

¹³For instance Ishiguro (1972) and Mondadori (1973).

¹⁴ See Cover & Hawthorne (1991) for an argument to the contrary.

Sleigh claims that Leibniz did not accept (3), even if he accepted superintrinsicism. According to Sleigh, this issue is at the heart of the disagreement over individual concepts between Arnauld and Leibniz in their correspondence. Arnauld seems to have accepted (3), which made him oppose Leibniz's thesis that a concept of an individual is their *complete* individual concept. Let us say that satisfying a predicate F is intrinsic to a if and only if anything that would not be F would be distinct from a (Sleigh 1990, p. 57). Let us suppose that a satisfies F essentially if and only if it is metaphysically impossible for a to exist and not be F (Sleigh 1990, p. 57). Then, it seems that Leibniz could endorse superintrinsicism, but not endorse superessentialism.

If Leibniz is not a superessentialist, then it seems that he should allow for the numerically identical individuals to be part of different possible worlds. If a predicate F that an individual a actually satisfies is not essential to a , then it is possible for a to be not F . Does this mean that Leibniz allows for a to be the numerically same individual as an individual at some non-actual possible world that is not F ? Should we take it that Leibniz allowed for transworld identity? There are plenty of passages in Leibniz's writings which suggest that he did not allow for transworld identity. For example, Leibniz writes in Theodicy (H, §414):

I will show you some [worlds], wherein shall be found, not absolutely the same Sextus as you have seen (*that is not possible, he carries with him always that which he shall be*) but several Sextuses resembling him. [my emphasis]

Furthermore, in the *Discourse on Metaphysics* (P, §30) Leibniz writes:

But someone else will say: how is it that this man [Judas] will certainly commit this sin? The reply is easy: namely, that otherwise he would not be this man. For God sees from all time that there will be a certain Judas,

whose notion or idea [concept], which God has, contains this future free action.

One could argue that the passage from the *Discourse* comes from a text where Leibniz did not state his infinite analysis conception. However, this would be to miss the point that the denial of trans-world identity is not only a conclusion of Leibniz's theoretical deliberations, but that it also serves an important theodicean purpose. As argued by Di Bella (2014, p. 13), the denial of trans-world identity by Leibniz is crucial to 'eliminate to any ground for lamenting one's destiny'. Judas cannot complain that God created the world so that Judas betrays Jesus, because if Judas were not to betray Jesus, he would be numerically distinct from Judas. This means that Leibniz would not allow for trans-world identity even after he introduced his infinite analysis conception.¹⁵

But there could be a more prosaic reason. When Leibniz talks about possible worlds and possible individuals often he is talking about them in the context of a discussion about God's creation of the world (e.g. in the *Discourse on Metaphysics* (P, §30)). Possible worlds can be interpreted as collections of complete individual concepts. The concepts that constitute the world are *compossible*, which means that they can be instantiated together (although what it exactly means is a controversial matter¹⁶), and maximal, which means that no other complete individual concept could be added to the collection and the collection still be compossible.¹⁷ Thus, God seems to be choosing between complete

¹⁵ One other reason to think that trans-world identity is not particularly suitable for Leibniz's system is Leibniz's insistence that it is not possible for there to be individuals in distinct possible worlds who are qualitatively identical until a time t and differ qualitatively after t (Adams 1994, p. 75-81). If this is the case, then Leibniz denies one of the strong intuitive reasons for holding that trans-world identity is possible.

¹⁶ It is a controversial issue how to understand the compossibility relation within Leibniz's philosophy. For a survey of accounts of compossibility see Messina & Rutherford (2009). For an in-depth treatment of compossibility see Brown & Chiek (eds.) (2016).

¹⁷ Adams (1994, Chapter 3) argues that very likely possible worlds have to be harmonious for Leibniz, because God would not seriously consider creating an unharmonious world. See Harmer (2018) for an analysis of the difference between 'possible worlds' and 'possible creations'.

individual concepts, which are given in his understanding. In such a context, the thesis that some two individual concepts are the concepts of numerically the same individual seems to be less plausible, as God's choice regarding which world is to be created precedes the existence of any created individual. If possible worlds are not used to define modal notions, but are used to demonstrate that God had freedom to choose a different world than he actually did, then there is less motivation to endorse trans-world identity.

So for Leibniz the counterparthood relation between possible Sextuses and the actual Sextus is not identity.

5.2 Counterpart relation as an equivalence relation on essential predicates (Mondadori 1973)

Fabrizio Mondadori (1973; 1975) has suggested that we can use David Lewis's (1968) counterpart theory to interpret *de re* modal statements such as 'Adam possibly did not have posterity'. This seems like a natural choice, given that we are interpreting Leibniz as being opposed to trans-world identity.¹⁸ However, Mondadori's strategy ignores Leibniz's infinite analysis conception. According to the infinite analysis account, necessity and possibility are not to be defined via possible worlds. I believe that we can set our goals a little lower than Mondadori. We don't have to require that the counterpart theory allows us to define the Leibnizian notions of necessity and possibility. However, we can use counterpart theory to analyse Leibniz's discourse about possible worlds and individuals and ask questions about the relation of between 'the actual Adam' and 'possible Adams'.

¹⁸ Mondadori defines counterparthood as a relation between individual concepts rather than individuals. Working with concepts rather than individuals seems to be a question of convenience: counterparthood could be easily defined as a relation between individuals.

Mondadori (1973, p. 98) claims that a is a counterpart of b if and only if a has all the properties that b has essentially and there is nothing more similar to b at a 's world than a is. Thus, Mondadori claims that for every individual b there are predicates contained in the complete individual concept of the individual that are *essential* to that individual.¹⁹ It should be noted that Mondadori (1973, p. 96) does not mean only that the set of essential predicates should include the essence of kinds or species to which b belongs, but also predicates that identify b as a particular member of the kind. Thus, for an individual b , there is a set of predicates Δ_b such that any possible individual that is a counterpart of b satisfies all the predicates in Δ_b . Furthermore, Mondadori (1973, p. 98) suggests that on this conception of counterparthood we can treat the counterpart relation as an equivalence relation.

There are several problems with Mondadori's account. Firstly, even as Mondadori conceives of the counterpart relation, it is not an equivalence relation. Mondadori claims that the thesis that it is an equivalence relation is assumed for 'pedagogical purposes'; however, one should be careful in making such claims. On the criterion of counterparthood outlined above, the counterpart relation is neither transitive nor symmetric. It is non-symmetric, because even if a satisfies all the predicates that are essential to b , it might be the case that b does not satisfy all the predicates that are essential to a . Furthermore, it seems that it might be the case that a satisfies all the predicates that are essential to b , but some of the predicates that are essential to b are not essential to a ; if this is the case then some counterparts of a will not be counterparts of b ,

¹⁹ The term 'essential' appears in Leibniz's writings in multiple contexts and is often interpreted differently by scholars. Robert Sleigh (1990, p. 57) uses 'essential' to mean the same as 'necessary'. On the other hand, Benson Mates (1986) states that Leibniz's 'special' use of the term 'essential' means something like 'permanent'. On this conception, Aleksander is essentially a man, because he is a man at any point in his life, whereas Aleksander is not essentially a king, because he is not a king at every point in his life (Mates 1986, p. 90). Mondadori seems to use the term 'essential' to mean *necessary*; however, his conception of necessity in Leibniz is distinct from the infinite analysis conception.

which means that the counterpart relation is not transitive. So, on the face of it, Mondadori defines a relation that is reflexive, non-symmetric, and non-transitive.

Secondly, if it is the case that all predicates that an individual satisfies are contained in its CIC and 'Caesar' refers to Caesar's CIC, then Mondadori's account suffers from the Identity Problem. The reasoning is just as described in the previous section: Mondadori wants to base his account of the counterpart relation on predicates that are necessarily satisfied by an individual substance; however, this cannot be done, because there are predicates (e.g. 'is identical to Caesar' in Caesar's case) that an individual substance necessarily satisfies that its counterparts cannot satisfy. Thus, Mondadori's account should be rejected.

5.3 Similarity based counterpart relation

Let's consider the similarity-based interpretation of the counterpart relation between possibilia. Famously, David Lewis (1968) based his account of the counterpart relation between on similarity. The relation is reflexive, non-transitive, and non-symmetric. For any possible individuals x and y , x is a counterpart of y if and only if:

- (i) x is sufficiently similar to y and
- (ii) there is nothing in x 's world that is more similar to y than x is.

We can use Lewis's idea to interpret Leibniz's talk about possibilia. For instance, when Leibniz talks about possible Sextuses, we can interpret his talk as referring to individuals in other possible world such that they satisfy (i) and (ii) above. Of course, there are some aspects of the Lewisian picture that Leibniz does not endorse. Leibniz is not a modal realist. Moreover, he would not endorse a Lewisian axiom that says that everything that exists is a part of a world: for Leibniz, God is not part of any world, because worlds are what God decides to

actualise. Similarly, Leibniz would be unlikely to accept the possibility of there being more than one counterpart of some x at one possible world (Mondadori 1973), which Lewis does accept.

There is some textual evidence to suggest that Leibniz had something like a similarity-based counterpart relation in mind when he engaged in discourse about possibilia. For instance, in the passage from Theodicy (H, §414) quoted in Section 5.1, Leibniz writes that the counterparts of Sextus are not identical to him, but *resemble* him. Furthermore, consider the case of the inhabitants of Keilah discussed by Leibniz: David asks the oracle whether the inhabitants of Keilah would surrender him to Saul had the city been put under siege. Leibniz argues that the reason why God knows what would happen (even if Keilah was actually not under siege) is that he considers the behaviour of the inhabitants of Keilah in a non-actual world (H, §42). Furthermore, Leibniz writes explicitly that God considers the actions of the non-actual inhabitants of Keilah that are as similar to the actual inhabitants of Keilah as possible (apart from the added condition that Keilah is under siege in the considered non-actual world) (H §42 and A VI.4.1789-1790).²⁰

Arguably, the strongest support for the similarity-based interpretation comes from the correspondence with Arnauld. Leibniz writes:

[...] speaking of several Adams, I was not taking Adam as a determinate individual, but as a person conceived of in general terms—that is, under circumstances which seem to us to determine Adam as an individual, but which in truth do not sufficiently determine him as one, such as when we

²⁰ Leibniz writes (A VI.4.1789-1790): Est verbi gratia scientia an Keilitae obsessi sint dedituri urbem Saulo, et scientia non de his Keilitis, quorum notio plena involvit non esse obsessos, sed de aliis Keilitis possibilibus, qui communia habent omnia cum istis praeter ea quae cohaerent cum hypothese obsessionis. [*Trans.*: It is for example, the knowledge of whether the inhabitants of Keilah if besieged will surrender the city to Saul, and the knowledge is not about these inhabitants of Keilah, whose complete concept involves not being besieged, but about other possible inhabitants of Keilah, who have everything in common with them except that which coheres with the hypothesis of the siege.]

mean by Adam the first man, whom God puts in a garden of pleasure and which he leaves because of sin, and from whose side God draws a woman. But all that does not determine him sufficiently well, and so there would be several disjunctively possible Adams, or several individuals whom all of that would fit. (WF, p. 110)

What makes possible Adams the counterparts of the actual Adam is the fact that they satisfy certain conditions that the actual Adam satisfies: being the first man, being placed in the garden of pleasure, being one from whose side God draws a woman etc. Counterparts of Adam all have to be similar to him in these respects. This gives us the support for the claim that the counterpart relation has to satisfy (i) – Adam’s counterparts have to be sufficiently similar to him. Moreover, Leibniz states that when writing about Adam (and possible Adams) he conceived of Adam in general terms, but which seem to allow us to determine Adam as an individual. A natural interpretation of this statement is that these general terms in which Adam is conceived of allow us to pick out his counterparts from among the individuals that exist in their respective worlds. This provides support for (ii) as a condition on the counterpart relation: if x is Adam’s counterpart, then there is nothing in x ’s world that is more similar to Adam than x is.

Therefore, there is textual evidence that similarity seems to be an important condition on counterparthood for Leibniz. Of course, the textual support for this interpretation is not ironclad, but the support is sufficient for us to adopt this interpretation (at least until evidence against the interpretation is presented).

There are also theoretical advantages to the similarity-based interpretation of the counterpart relation in Leibniz’s discourse about possibilia. Importantly, such a counterpart relation is not vulnerable to the Identity Problem, which makes the interpretation stand out among other candidates discussed above. The interpretation of the counterpart relation based on similarity gives us

enough flexibility to interpret Leibniz's modal discourse and it is a charitable interpretation of Leibniz's writings in the context of his philosophical system.

6 Conclusion

Even though Leibniz endorsed the infinite analysis conception of modal notions, possibilia and possible worlds played an important role for him; in particular, Leibniz needed to employ these notions to solve the Problem of Contingency. In the paper I attempted to show that the Problem of Identity poses a serious problem to the formulation of the counterpart relation in Leibniz's philosophy. It turns out that we cannot straightforwardly employ the infinite analysis conception to work out a conception of the counterpart relation. I postulated that an interpretation of Leibniz's counterpart relation as a version of the Lewisian counterpart relation based on similarity is the best one. Given the Identity Problem and some textual support from Leibniz writings, this should be our interpretation of Leibniz's discourse about possibilia.

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